

YOGA FOR HEALTH AND WELLNESS

Km Roopa Sharma P.hD Scholar Amity University Noida

Email: roopasharma1996@gmail.com

Abstract

Yoga is an ancient remedy to the present modern problems. It is an ancient system of relaxation, exercise, and healing with origins in Indian philosophy. Yoga has gained a popularity around the world during the last century. Yoga, as many people often agree to, is not merely a method to attain mental peace, but also a powerful technique to get rid of ignorance which causes various kinds of suffering in human life. Swami Vivekananda has defined education, "It is the manifestation of divine perfection already reached in man". Swamiji wanted to see "man-making education".

It emphasises on life-building, man-making, character-making, assimilation of ideas. The very essence of education is concentration of mind, not the collecting of facts. In ancient times, people used to go to sages to learn wisdom and to get answers to the fundamental questions of life. This was seen in all ancient civilisations - India and China, in particular. However, over the century's education has retreated from that position. We no longer claim to give wisdom, we give only information, our schools no longer give moral and spiritual values, only secular subjects are taught. The very much need of the education system by which character is formed, strength of mind is gained, the intellect is expanded, and by which one can stand on one's own feet. Yoga is not simply Asanas and Pranayama's, it's much deeper than this. It also involves certain moral and ethical practices. These moral practices are known as Yamas and Niyamas. No educational system is effective unless it incorporates into itself these virtuous practices.

Keywords: Yoga, Wellness, Education

Introduction

Yoga is a practice of mental and physical exercise, which aims to acquire a good health in life an individual. Holistic health, integrative treatment and mind, body medicine are some of the current buzz words in health care originated from yoga, which took its birth some 5000 years ago in India and is one of the elements of Ayurvedic medicine as the healing science.

Yoga practices are gaining popularity and have the potential to make a significant contribution to the field of health sciences. Having a wide array of practice, all essentially including breathing exercises, physical postures and meditation, the science and art of yoga is reaching new heights. Associated with a series of behavioural modifications that contribute to a healthy lifestyle, traditional yoga is a philosophy for living.

The practice improves mood and reduces stress utilising mind/body strategies designed to promote good health that covers relaxation techniques, hypnosis, visualisation, feedback, meditation, autogenic, cognitive behavioural therapy, group therapy and spirituality. Recently, scientists have explored its consistent beneficial biochemical, physiological, psychological effects in human beings. Yoga based training normalises the functions of the autonomic nervous system by maintaining both sympathetic and parasympathetic indices toward normal.

World Health organisation and other policy makers on Healthcare system are striving a lot to adopt holistic healthcare measures which can be effective in the prevention of lifestyle and psychosomatic diseases such as insomnia , diabetes mellitus, obesity, hypertension etc.

Yoga is an ancient Indian practice and a way of life that includes regulated breathing, maintaining various postures and meditation. The word “yoga” comes from Sanskrit and means “to yoke” or join. The focus is on the union of mind and body or the harmony of body, breath, and mind. Patanjali formally described the practice of yoga in the treatise of Yoga. He defined yoga as the process of eliminating all thoughts in the mind and

allowing it to settle down to silence. Attainment of such an equity, ultimately leads to a balanced and healthy mind and body. Yoga is a systematic process of calming down the mind and Maharshi Patanjali advocated systematic practice which include Yama (external ethics), niyama (internal ethics), asanas (postures), pranayama (regulated breathing), pratyahara (detachment), dharna (concentration), dhyana (meditation), and samadhi (detached awareness of self) aimed toward attainment of self-realisation or the inner blissful state.

Among these, asanas, pranayama, and meditation are popular and have been used as a therapy for decades. Health is precious treasure of an individual who is looking to lead a meaningful life. In the current scenario, it is quite challenging to enjoy the best productivity for a person through the good physical and mental health. The advancement in science and technology has increased the sedentary and semi-sedentary lifestyle leading to lack of physical activity. In addition to this, stressful situations are also contributing a lot for the rise in psychosomatic diseases.

Ashtanga yoga of sage Patanjali is one of the most comprehensive methodologies for the development of holistic healthcare model-based sustainability for global health, peace and environmental concerns. The research in yoga has shown that its therapeutic values are helpful for health promotion and disease prevention. The principles and practices of Yoga in the form of therapy are being used as preventative, complementary and alternative medicine in dealing with various physical and mental disorders. Social approach, cost-effective and eco-friendly characteristics are the important factors for sustainability of any system, and these are effectively achieved in yoga for gaining numerous health benefits on multiple dimensions of health concepts.

Ashtanga Yoga of Maharishi Patanjali

The classical work of Yoga sutras of Sage Patanjali is one of the most authentic guides on the principles and practices of Yoga which is based on the sankya philosophy. Ethical preparation, control of the mind and body and development of the spiritual journey is explained in the Yoga sutras.

The practice of Ashtanga Yoga is useful in the reduction of the impurities and attainment of the highest wisdom. They are:

- Yama: Universal morality
- Niyama: Personal observances
- Asanas: Body postures
- Pranayama: Regulation of breath
- Pratyahara: Control of the senses
- Dharna: Concentration
- Dhyana: Meditation on the divine
- Samadhi: Union with the divine

Relevance of Yoga in Social Health

The principles of Yoga called as yamas and niyamas are effective in purifying the impurities in moral behaviour which are more serious issues for the social health. Will power, intellect, and stability on the emotions is attained through the practice of these disciplines. It helps to promote social-emotional development in individual life. The social harmony and self-acceptance level improves for the wellness of the society. To be present in the moment by focusing their attention on their breath, as a result, their concentration and focus improves.

Promotion of Physical Health

Yogic interventions are known to affect physical health by improving muscular endurance, muscular strength, flexibility increasing motor control. The practice of Asanas and pranayama are effectively for improvement of strength and flexibility, enhance the joints range motion and blood circulation.

Conceivably, *asanas* particularly have a positive effect on fitness and physical flexibility with a secondary effect on the mental state, while the *pranayama* practices and relaxation techniques may result in greater awareness, less stress, and higher well-being and quality of life.

Yoga for Mental Health

The inner conflicts, stressful conditions are known to affect our mental health. The philosophical foundation of yogic principles and practices of Pranayama and meditation harness the mental harmony to develop the peace of mind, serenity which is an antidote in the prevention of mental health issues.

Yoga boost mood by lowering levels of stress hormones, increasing the production of feel-good chemicals known as endorphins, and bringing more oxygenated blood to your brain. But yoga may have additional benefits. It can affect mood by elevating levels of a brain chemical called gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA), which is associated with better mood and decreased anxiety.

Regulation of Emotions

Emotional balance is within your reach when you cultivate the intelligence of both your body and mind. An integrative approach to healing anxiety, depression, and chronic stress through yoga and breathing exercises. This is an important teaching for maintaining stable emotional health.

Health in Spirituality

Yoga is essentially spiritual discipline. Spiritual health includes a purposeful life, transcendence and actualisation of different dimensions and capacities of human beings. Spiritual health creates a balance between physical, psychological and social aspects of human life.

The sages and saints have walked the great path to fulfil the aim of the meaningful life which is filled with inner harmony and happiness.

Yoga in Diseases

Yoga has proved to have a positive impact on dealing with physical and psychological ailments.

Yoga is a great way to get rid of diseases and health conditions from cardiac problems to depression. There exists a body of research suggesting that yoga is the best healing therapy for improving spine alignment and joint health. But on the flip side, research also suggests that yoga can't cure cancers though it can help one deal with chemotherapy. The intent of yoga is to create well-being as a result of physical, emotional, mental, social, and spiritual balance. This is also the intent of medicine, as defined by the World Health Organisation. While the entire focus of yoga is to create such a balance to prevent diseases, yoga can be used to cure or manage diseases as well.

Yoga and Lifestyle

Yoga integrates physical postures (asanas) to enhance flexibility, strength, and balance, promoting better posture and joint health. It incorporates mindfulness and meditation to reduce stress, anxiety, and depression, improving mental clarity, focus, and emotional resilience. Through breathwork (pranayama) and meditation, yoga cultivates emotional awareness and self-regulation, fostering stability and positivity. Yoga enhances the mind-body connection, promoting holistic health and self-awareness by encouraging awareness of physical sensations. It advocates for healthy lifestyle habits like mindful eating, regular exercise, and sufficient sleep, emphasizing self-care and body awareness.

Conclusion

Yoga is a holistic science and art of living. This is because routines Yoga Asanas (poses), Pranayama breathing techniques and Kriyas (cleansing exercises) prescribed in Yoga help to tone up the whole system.

As yoga practitioners have always known, intuitively and experientially, yoga doesn't just make you feel good. These practices have real, concrete results for the mind and body—they positively impact everything from the brain and biochemistry to BMI and

blood glucose levels. This is not a placebo effect; you don't have to "believe" in yoga for it to work. When you practice regularly over a significant period, these changes will occur.

References

1. Siddappa, Naragatti, Management of Hypertension through Yogic practices, international journal of AYUSH 2018.
2. Naragatti S, Yoga and Health, Journal of advanced research in ayurveda yoga unani siddha and homeopathy-2018.
3. A study of response pattern of non-insulin dependent diabetes to yoga therapy. Diabetes Research and Clinical Practice 1993
4. Javnbakht M, Hejazi Kenari R, Ghasemi M. Effects of yoga on depression and anxiety of women. Complement Ther Clin Pract 2009 May.
5. Joshi LN, Joshi VD, Gokhale LV. Effects of short term 'Pranayam' practice on breathing rate and ventilatory function of lung. Indian J Physiol Pharmacol 1992
6. Joshi M, Telles S. Immediate effects of right and left nostril breathing on verbal and spatial scores. Indian J Physiol Pharmacol 2008
7. Raghavendra RM, Nagarathna R, Nagendra HR et al.
8. Influence of yoga program on post operative outcomes & wound healing in early operable breast cancer pattern undergoing surgery. International Journal of Yoga 2008.
9. Raghavendra RM, Nagarathna R, Nagendra HR et al. Anxiolytics effects of a yoga program in early breast cancer patients undergoing conventional treatment: a randomized controlled trial. Complementary Therapies in Medicine 2009.
10. Sahu RJ, Bhole MV. Effects of two types of pranava (Omkar) recitation on psychomotor performance. Yoga-Mimamsa 1983.
11. Indian J Community Med. 2014 Apr-Jun; 39(2) Yoga and Health, Davendra Kumar Taneja.
12. Yoga for health and wellness, National health portal of India. http://nhp.gov.in/yoga-for-health-and-wellness_mtl
13. Art of Living, yoga for health and wellness.